

Ethno-nationalism, Linguistic Identity and the Political Autonomy: A comparative study of Mahagujarat & Bahawalpur

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Abstract

Ethnicity becomes impressionable when it achieves the awareness of its uniqueness. There will be least a country in the world which is based on a nation ideology. In modern times the concept of nation is changed into nation-state in which different ethnic groups develop an identity as ethno-nationalism. As India and Pakistan had been a colony of the British crown and both the countries gained independence at the same time. But in case of policy making related demarcation of the states and autonomy, both countries have opted different methodologies. In this regard many of princely states had to fight for their autonomy according to the Indian Act 1935. History witnessed commonalities in both the countries Pakistan & India related to the issue of autonomy on behalf of ethnicity. In 1970 the Gujarat achieved its federalization on account of ethnic disparity but in case of Bahawalpur, princely state has great hindrance in achieving federalization although the model is same. There are many things common in the model of achieving federalization in Gujarat (India) and the Bahawalpur (Pakistan). The study will examine the model of autonomy for the Mahagujarat and the Bahawalpur keeping in view the ethno nationalism and linguistic disparities.

Keywords: Federalization, Ethno-Nationalism, Princely State, Linguistic Disparities, History.

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